

PROBING THE LUNAR SUBSURFACE: A MULTI-SCALE GEOPHYSICAL PAYLOAD. A. Frigeri¹, D. Piero¹, C. Rossi¹, A. Parmentier¹, R. Vaccaro¹, F. de Angelis¹, A. Rubini, A. Bigazzi², E. Ammannito², G. Mascetti²; ¹Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali (IAPS), Italian National Institute for Astrophysics (INAF), Roma, Italy (alessandro.frigeri@inaf.it), ² Italian Space Agency (ASI), Rome, Italy

Introduction: The lunar subsurface is characterized by a highly fractured regolith–megaregolith layer, typically extending to depths of 1–3 km before transitioning to more competent crustal material, reflecting the cumulative impact and volcanic processes that have shaped the Moon throughout its geologic evolution [1]. The underground of the Moon hides structures like volcanic layers, craters, voids or fractures and, in the case of the polar region, it probably hosts underground resources like ice. Most of the missions landed on the Moon during the space race of the 1960’s included direct and indirect investigations of the subsurface through different techniques. Geophysical imaging methods allow us to map the subsurface non-invasively, offering constraints to tie the geologic interpretation of the organization of materials and processes in the underground.

The Payload: The INAF-ASI *Multi-scale Geophysical Imaging of Lunar Subsurface* is a concept for a payload suite focused on geological exploration of the shallow subsurface of the Moon through geophysical imaging operated at the surface of the Moon by a robotic platform or a human crew. Its architectural design prioritizes flexibility through reconfigurability, aiming at different operating scenarios from the middle latitude to the poles. The suite comprises a ground penetrating radar (GPR) and a magnetometer (MAG), enabling active and passive geophysical investigations of the subsurface over depths ranging from a few meters to the first hundred meters, with spatial resolutions spanning from tens of centimeters to meters, depending on the instrumental component.

Objectives: Main goals of the payload suite are: 1) understanding the history of the Solar System and the Moon’s formation by studying the mega-regolith structure at the human and robotic exploration scale 2) solving specific geologic questions, such as magnetic anomalies that do exhibit albedo variation but not morphologic evidence and 3) enabling future human and robotic exploration at the lunar surface through resource identification and hazard detection, possibly in synergy with reconnaissance missions indicating the most suitable survey area.

The GPR component of the suite is being developed using Software Defined Radio (SDR) hardware implementing a Frequency Modulated radar signal spanning from 200 to 1200 MHz [2,3]. The use of SDR technology offers compact and lightweight implementation, with modest power requirements. Our prototype is ex-

pected to weight less than 500 grams with a volume of around 300 cubic centimeters, and the power consumption will be around 10W or less depending on the operative mode. The instrument software is implemented in ANSI C on a GNU/Linux–based embedded real-time platform and leverages state-of-the-art Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) libraries, guaranteeing future adaptation to different spacecraft payload interfaces.

The MAG component is based on a compact design optimized for identifying the shape and depth of complex, 3D underground structures [4,5]. Testing on the MAG component will make use of INAF-IAPS’s magnetic chamber facility to null the magnetic field, simulating the lunar environments.

The two experiment components prototypes are being developed in-house at INAF-IAPS laboratories in Rome, Italy, utilizing readily available commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components to accelerate the prototyping and testing phases, reducing development time and cost. Prototypes are expected to reach TRL 3–4 within the 24-month project timeline, with terrestrial analog testing included where feasible as a cost-effective precursor to TRL 5–6 validation.

Conclusions: In a highly dynamic and international lunar exploration context, we are developing our experiment with an adaptable technology intended to support a wide range of operational scenarios for surveying the lunar subsurface. The INAF–ASI payload concept for *Multi-scale Geophysical Imaging of Lunar Subsurface* aims to deliver an advanced instrument suite for the geological investigation of the lunar underground, establishing also the technological and methodological groundwork required to meet the challenges posed by the new generation of lunar missions, which demand a high degree of flexibility and adaptability within an international exploration framework.

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